
INNOVATIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH TO YOUNG CHILDREN

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Abstract

Since our country's independence, there has been a strong emphasis on learning foreign languages in our country. On December 10, 2012, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan issued a resolution "On the further improvement of the system of learning foreign languages," and the introduction of foreign languages in the first grades of secondary schools began in the 2013-2014 school year. Nowadays, foreign languages, especially English, are taught not only to students of schools, lyceums, colleges, and universities but also to children in kindergarten and employees working in various fields. Of course, there's a reason behind this.

This article discusses new approaches to teaching a foreign language to young learners as well as keeping students interested and engaged more.

Keywords

Modern techniques, innovative methods, mental and physical activities.

Introduction

Innovative teaching techniques are more than simply employing cutting-edge technology in class or staying up to date on the latest educational trends; these are the teaching-learning approaches!

They are all about implementing new teaching practices that are more student-centered. These unique ones allow students to participate actively and communicate with their peers as well as you, the instructor, throughout sessions. Students will have to work more, but in a way, that better fulfills their requirements and allows them to learn quicker.

Unlike traditional teaching, which is primarily concerned with how much knowledge you can provide to your students, innovative methods of teaching delve deeply into what learners genuinely take away from what you're teaching during lectures.

Learning the languages of economically, scientifically, and culturally developed countries is the main factor in mastering the achievements of world science and development. Language learning also depends on age periods. According to psychologists, children learn a language faster and easier than adults. The main reasons for this are the natural tendency of children to learn languages, the fact that they have a strong ability to imitate, and the fact that children have more time than adults. It should be considered that 6-7-year-old children can not understand the meaning of information, but memorize it mechanically. Because of this, it is necessary not to start teaching English to primary school students with grammatical concepts. Otherwise, from the first step of learning a foreign language, it is possible to strain the child and extinguish his/her interest. Therefore, teaching a foreign language to young children is challenging and requires a great deal of patience and responsibility.

Nowadays, many teachers aim to keep their classes as far away from that scenario as possible, allowing students to get more involved in their learning by experimenting with different approaches to teaching.

The following methods can be used to teach children English in a meaningful and interesting way:

1) subject environment; if the teacher can create that environment depending on the subject, children will learn the language better. For example, traveling, birthdays, in the kitchen, etc. On the topic of traveling, the teacher organizes a trip, and information about the importance of traveling (foot, bicycle, automobile, train, boat, airplane), where to travel (Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, England, USA) will give. This hoi strengthens students' vocabulary, and language abilities, and expands their worldview.

2) to teach the topic via songs and poems. For example, it can be shown that children learn the English alphabet by singing rather than simply memorizing it.

3) games related to mental and physical activities;

a) riddles; children have a strong interest in finding answers to riddles. Therefore, when the teacher says the riddle in English or Uzbek, he should ask the children to say the answer in English. Then children learn words quickly.

b) role-play. The teacher should role-play or play it to children while teaching some information, for example, the names of animals or birds. For example: if one student shows the howling of a dog and the meowing of a cat, another student needs to find out which animal these sounds belong to and say its English name.

4) cartoons;

While children do not understand the words in the cartoon during language learning, they try to understand the words they use through the actions of the cartoon characters. This is an interesting and effective way for children to learn the language.

5) practical training (tasting fruits and other foods, smelling flowers); This sentence can be explained by the thoughts of a practicing psychologist: "A teacher who wants something to be firmly fixed in the children's memory should use as many of the child's sensory organs as possible: eyes, ears, sound organs, muscle sensations, and even if possible, he should try to involve the organs of smell and taste in the process of remembering". For example: when a teacher tastes an apple, its color is red or green, He should give information about the smell of sweet (tasty) or sour, and fragrant and feed the fruits to other students and ask them to give information about that fruit in English. it also helps in their further learning. If the teacher asks the students the English name of the colors, the child immediately remembers the time when he ate the fruit, he quickly remembers that it is red-red, green-green. So, using such a method helps the student's information in the long-term memory and ensures that it remains.

6) through gestures, and facial expressions; When the teacher says something to the child or gives an order, for example, it is understandable to the child if he uses gestures in sentences such as come here, open the book, stand up, look at the blackboard. . - through visual aids, posters, books; - writing on things that are visible and often used in everyday life. For example: writing on a door, book, table, blackboard, window, etc. Since such things are always visible and often used in practice, the child learns these words involuntarily.

7) through the news; We know that children are curious. They quickly get bored with the sameness. Therefore, it is necessary to teach them not always use the same methods but to change and update such methods. Otherwise, children will understand how the teacher will teach and prepare for it. Teaching with innovative methods raises children's aspirations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, language teaching to young children should be conducted as an interesting activity, not as a duty, and learning using several effective methods can serve as a foundation for their future knowledge. The education field is developing at such a rapid pace that you must keep up and adapt to more up-to-date methods. Otherwise, you may struggle to fit in.

REFERENCES:

1. John Adams II Analysis of retirement age in different countries of the world.London 2017.
2. –Chet tillarni o'rganish tizimini yanada takomillashtirish chora -tadbirlari to'g'risida (PQ-1875-son)IXalq so'zi gazetasi. 2012yil. 12-dekabr.
3. J. Jalolov . –ingliz tilini o'qitish metodlaril –O'qituvchil nashiryoti Toshkent To'Xtasinova, N. R. Q., & Soibjonova, M. T. O. Q. (2022). TAGMA'NO VA PRESUPPOZITSIYA HODISASINING PRAGMATIK TADQIQI (Abdulla Qahhor asarlari misolida). Central Asian Research Journal for Interdisciplinary Studies (CARJIS), 2(4), 141-146.
4. Тухтасинова, Н. Р. (2021). ИССЛЕДОВАНИЕ ПРЕДВАРИТЕЛЬНЫХ И ТАГМАНСКИХ СОБЫТИЙ НА РАБОТАХ АБДУЛЛЫ КАХХАР. Экономика и социум, (2-2), 240-244.
5. Pratoва, G. O., & To'Xtasinova, N. R. Q. (2022). O'ZBEK TILIDA FREZELOGIZMLARNING PRAGMATIK SINONIMYASI. Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences, 2(5), 35-38.